

Effect of Green façade on Improved Indoor Air Quality

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Abstract

This article explores the benefits of green facades in improving indoor air quality (IAQ) and their potential impact on energy efficiency. Green facades, also known as living walls or vertical gardens, are vertical structures covered with plants that can be installed both indoors and outdoors. They have gained attention in the field of sustainable architecture due to their ability to provide multiple advantages, including enhanced IAQ and energy efficiency.

The research presented in this article is based on a comprehensive review of existing literature, real-world data, and simulation tools. The findings highlight the significant role of green facades in air purification, reduction of harmful pollutants, and the overall well-being of building occupants. Green facades act as natural insulators, minimizing heat absorption in the summer and heat loss in the winter, thus reducing the energy needed for cooling and heating a building.

The article also discusses the various types of green facades, such as direct greening, indirect greening, and living wall systems, and their potential applications in different climate conditions and building types. Additionally, it provides a visual representation of the process by which green facades contribute to improving IAQ, including the absorption of carbon dioxide and harmful air pollutants.

The effectiveness of green facades in improving IAQ and energy efficiency remains significant. Incorporating green facades into smart building design can contribute to creating healthier and more sustainable indoor environments, reduce air pollution, and enhance the well-being of building occupants.

Keywords: Indoor air quality, green façade, energy efficiency, living wall, passive air purification

1. Introduction

Green facades, also known as living walls or vertical gardens, have the potential to significantly enhance indoor air quality. These structures function by purifying the air through the presence of numerous plants, which filter toxins and generate oxygen [1, 2] as a consequence they are also called biofiltration.

In urban areas where greenery is limited, green walls prove particularly beneficial in improving air quality both indoors and outdoors.

Plants can absorb approximately 25% of carbon emissions resulting from human activity, and living walls offer a greater number of plants to filter toxins and convert carbon dioxide into oxygen. Moreover, the cleaner air provided by green facades can lead to reduced health issues such as respiratory problems and allergies, thereby contributing to enhanced employee well-being and productivity in indoor spaces such as corporate offices. Additionally, green facades can aid in improving energy efficiency within buildings by providing insulation, thus reducing the need for excessive heating and cooling. Furthermore, they can help regulate indoor temperatures, resulting in energy savings.

Green facades can be classified into three main types: direct greening, indirect greening, and living wall systems [3]. Direct greening involves the wall directly supporting climber plants, while indirect greening utilizes a specially designed support structure with an air gap between the wall and plants. Living wall systems employ fixed boxes on the wall, serving as a base for plant growth without the need for climbing [4].

Depending on their configuration, these systems may require irrigation and can accommodate heavier plants, even trees. By integrating green facades into building design, architects can contribute to the creation of healthier and more sustainable indoor environments, reducing air pollution and enhancing indoor air quality [5].

2. Literature review

A green facade is a type of vertical garden where climbing plants or cascading groundcovers are trained to cover specially designed supporting structures on the exterior of a building. Green facades and living walls offer numerous benefits, including improved indoor air quality, aesthetics, and the potential to reduce the reliance on mechanical ventilation. By integrating biofiltration clouds into natural ventilation systems, architects and building designers can create healthier and more sustainable indoor environments, enhancing the overall well-being of occupants [6]. Some of the key characteristics and benefits of green facades include:

Improves Air Quality: Green facades help filter the air and remove pollutants, contributing to better indoor and outdoor air quality [7] (Figure 2).

They can also help in capturing fine particulate matter, although the effectiveness may vary.

Reduces Urban Heat Island Effect: In dense urban areas, the replacement of green areas with hard surfaces leads to the conversion of sunlight to heat, creating the urban heat island effect. Green facades can help mitigate this effect by promoting the cooling process in buildings and retaining rainwater [7].

Enhances Aesthetic Appearance: Green facades can elevate the exteriors of buildings, making them visually appealing and inspiring [7].

They can also contribute to the overall architectural identity of a structure and bring it to life.

Saves Energy: By reducing the energy requirements of buildings, green facades contribute to energy savings and promote sustainable architecture in urban environments [7].

Provides Habitat for Urban Creatures: Green facades can serve as habitats for various urban creatures, including butterflies, birds, and insects, contributing to urban biodiversity [8].

Acoustic Solutions: Green facades can help dampen noise from the outside, providing acoustic comfort inside buildings [8].

Flexible Design Options: Green facades can be designed with a variety of plant species, including evergreens or deciduous plants, depending on the desired effect.

They can also feature containers at various levels, especially in multi-story buildings, to create a more dynamic and visually interesting façade.

Green façade or Biofiltration is a technique that can be used to remove and control air pollutants. These include low operating and capital costs, effective removal of compounds, low-pressure drops, and no further waste streams produced [9, 10].

Figure 1 :A green facade not only adds life to a building but also has energy-saving and noise-reducing qualities. Inhabitants can enjoy the comforts of nature even in a busy city [11].

Figure 2: indoor garden with integrated smart technology that improves indoor air quality, and aesthetics and ensures healthy moisture levels [12].

Green facades can be categorized into different types based on their structure and installation method. The main types of green facades are:

Ground-based facades: In this system, the greenery is grown upwards from ground level, either from the soil, pots, or planter boxes. Ground systems typically use self-clinging plants (such as ivy) or a support structure like a steel trellis for climbing plants [13].

Facade-bound systems: These systems involve the installation of support structures directly on the building facade, with the greenery growing vertically from the structure. Examples include stainless-steel mesh for climbing plants and steel wire rope for pre-grown green wall panels [13].

Mixed systems: These systems combine elements of both ground-based and facade-bound systems, incorporating various support structures and planting methods to create a unique green facade design [13].

Direct green facades: In this type, vegetation is planted directly into the soil, or a substrate attached to the facade. These solutions can be costly and fragile due to the intensive care and maintenance required, including regular watering and fertilizing [14].

Indirect green facades: Indirect green facades involve the use of planter boxes or other containers to hold the plants, which are then attached to the building facade. This type of green facade is more flexible and easier to maintain compared to direct green facades [15].

Figure 3: the differences between the green facade types [13].

Figure 4: Type of green walls [16]

Green facades or biofiltration designs have appeared advantageous in terminating dangerous pollutants from wastewater or contaminated air [17], they can also be used to prevent the entry of polluted air into indoor spaces [18]. A green facade is a type of air pollution control technology that uses microorganisms and fungi to biologically assimilate,

and process vapor phase volatile organic compounds (VOCs) and smelly compounds commonly found in industrial and urban areas [10, 17, 19, 20].

Typically, plants with denser roots are used in this system, and microbe growth is encouraged by placing roots between synthetic fabric layers [6, 21, 22]. This process is based on two principal phenomena: the transfer of contaminants from the air to the water phase or support medium and the bioconversion of pollutants to biomass, metabolic end-products, or carbon dioxide and water [23].

Indoor air green façades are a completely natural method of maintaining the quality of indoor air and have become recognized as an exceptionally functional and very aesthetic system that can truly enhance indoor environments in many ways [18]. The principles behind indoor air biofiltration involve passing a contaminated air or water stream through a biologically active substrate where beneficial microbes use the pollutants, such as VOCs, as a food source [18]. The biofilter substrate can be made of a variety of materials, including peat moss, coconut coir, and perlite [24]. Dust particles collected in the biofilter are then washed away by the flowing water cascading down as part of the hydroponic process [18].

Biofiltration systems, such as botanical biofilters and active living walls, combine the benefits of natural ventilation and biofiltration to create a healthier and more sustainable indoor environment. In the context of natural ventilation, biofiltration clouds can be integrated into the building's design to facilitate the airflow and filtration process. The chimney effect, where warm air rises and creates a pressure difference, can be utilized to draw air through the biofilter media, which is typically a bed of biological material such as wood chips. [6, 18, 25]. They can provide clean indoor air directly to an adjacent space or distribute it throughout the building's HVAC system[18].

Research has found that active botanical biofilter systems are efficient in filtering indoor air pollutants, as well as providing a refreshing environment [24, 26]. Therefore, biofiltration can be an effective method to prevent the entry of polluted air into indoor spaces and utilized in various forms to enhance air quality [27].

some of the best biofiltration methods that prevent the entry of pollutants into indoor spaces include:

1. **Active Botanical Biofiltration (ABB):**

Green facades, also known as living walls or vertical gardens, are vertical structures covered with vegetation that can be installed on the exterior or interior of a building.

They offer several benefits for indoor air quality:

Air Filtration: Green facades can filter and purify the air by using living plants and their associated microorganisms. This biological-based treatment method, known as a biofilter, is efficient in removing indoor air pollutants, including particulate matter (PM), formaldehyde, and toluene.

Particulate Matter Removal: Research has shown that active botanical biofilter (ABB) systems, such as green facades, can achieve removal efficiencies ranging from 54% to 85% for total suspended particulate matter (TSP).

Gaseous Pollutant Removal: In real environments, green facades have demonstrated high removal efficiencies for gaseous pollutants, with formaldehyde removal rates of 90% and over 33% for toluene [28].

Energy and Capital Efficiency: Biofiltration techniques, such as green facades, require lower energy and capital investments compared to other air treatment methods, making them a sustainable and cost-effective solution for improving indoor air quality [25].

Aesthetic and Biophilic Benefits: In addition to their air purification capabilities, green facades enhance the aesthetic appearance of buildings, provide a refreshing environment, and contribute to the overall well-being of occupants [29-31].

2. **Active living walls (ALW):**

vertical structure covered with vegetation that can be installed on the exterior or interior of a building [30, 31].

It is a type of biofilter, a biological-based treatment method that uses living plants and their associated microorganisms to filter and purify the air. Green facades offer several benefits for indoor air quality and the overall well-being of occupants [32, 33]:

Air Filtration: Green facades can effectively filter and purify the air, removing pollutants such as particulate matter (PM), volatile organic compounds (VOCs), carbon monoxide (CO), and carbon dioxide (CO₂).

Aesthetic and Biophilic Benefits: In addition to their air purification capabilities, green facades enhance the visual appearance of buildings, provide a refreshing environment, and contribute to the overall well-being of occupants.

Passive and Active Systems: Green facades can be passive, relying on natural airflow to filter pollutants, or active, using a mechanical system to force air through the plants. Active living walls have been shown to significantly reduce VOCs by 72.5% [34].

Temperature and Humidity Control: Some green facades can be upgraded to control indoor temperature as a heating and cooling system, as well as humidity, by utilizing an integrated water delivery system [21, 35, 36].

Residential and Commercial Applications: Green facades can be used in various types of buildings, including residential and commercial structures, to improve indoor air quality and create a healthier and more sustainable environment for occupants.

Active biofiltration entails employing biological systems to cleanse the air, while active living walls are systems that enable the growth of vegetation on vertical surfaces such as building facades or indoor walls. An active living wall can function as a form of active biofiltration by compelling air to traverse the vegetated wall, harnessing its evaporative cooling capabilities and air purification potential [35]. In other words, while an active living wall can serve as an active biofiltration system, not all active biofiltration systems can be classified as active living walls [36].

Figure 5: Vertical Gardening - Vertical Garden Green Wall Living Wall Biofilter [37].

3. **Indoor Air Biofilters:** These are completely natural systems that use a biologically active substrate to remove air pollutants. The biofilter substrate can be made of various materials, such as peat moss, coconut coir, and perlite. Dust particles, including PM, collected in the biofilter are then washed away by the flowing water cascading down as part of the hydroponic process[18].
4. **Integration with HVAC Systems:** Indoor air biofilters can be integrated into a building's HVAC system to distribute clean air throughout the indoor spaces. This ensures that the filtered air is effectively circulated and reduces the entry of PM and other pollutants [18].
5. **High Airflow Rates:** Biofilters designed to deliver high airflow rates, such as 50 liters of "virtual outside air" per square meter of biofilter per second, can effectively filter and prevent the entry of PM into indoor spaces [18].
Biofiltration can be designed to deliver high airflow rates by considering the following factors:
 - a) **Fan Selection:** Fans should be selected based on the design airflow rate and pressure drop. Typical agricultural ventilating fans are selected for biofiltration.[38]
 - b) **Horizontal Airflow:** Research has shown that the airflow resistance of biofilter media consisting of woodchips and mature compost is significantly lower with horizontal airflow. Therefore, designing biofilters with horizontal airflow can help achieve high airflow rates[39].
 - c) **Watering Rate:** Applying a higher watering rate for biofilter sides or sections that have lower moisture content can help distribute airflow and media moisture content across the biofilter [40].
6. **Combination with Other Air Purification Methods:** Biofiltration methods can be combined with other air purification techniques, such as activated carbon filters or

electrostatic precipitators, to enhance the removal of PM and other pollutants from indoor air [15, 29].

[41] By considering these factors, biofiltration can be designed to deliver high airflow rates, which can effectively filter and prevent the entry of PM and other pollutants into indoor spaces.

In conclusion, biofiltration systems, such as botanical biofilters and active living walls, play a crucial role in maintaining indoor air quality and can be designed to deliver high airflow rates for effective filtration. These systems require maintenance, and cleaning, and may have varying levels of durability. ABB systems, for example, use activated carbon and water for pollutant adsorption and absorption, which may necessitate periodic replacement or replenishment of these materials to maintain their effectiveness [28, 42].

Some biofilters are designed to be self-cleaning, relying on natural processes or mechanical systems to keep the filter media clean. For instance, a DIY backyard pond with a self-cleaning biofilter can be built using rocks and pebbles to create a filter pond. The biofilter media is kept in motion by air bubbles from an air pump, providing optimal conditions for the nitrifying bacteria [43]. Additionally, self-cleaning strainers and filters can be used, eliminating the need for replacement cartridges by employing a backwash system that can be controlled either fully automatically or semi-automatically [44].

Moreover, the filter's elasticity and pulsatile flow contribute to its self-cleaning abilities, and these principles could be applied to the design of biofilters for wastewater treatment or aquaculture systems [45]. Passive self-cleaning biofilters are a type of biofilter that uses natural processes to keep the filter media clean. They require little maintenance and can be used in various applications such as reducing odor emissions, treating raw water, and managing stormwater. Examples of passive self-cleaning biofilters include bio-inspired [46] surface modification and water polishers [47]. These systems are cost-effective and environmentally friendly as they rely on natural processes for their operation [48].

3. Methodology

The purpose of this research is to analyze how green facades impact indoor air quality. Our focus is to explore how external green facades can prevent pollutants from entering indoor spaces and subsequently purify the indoor air using various indoor green facade methods. To gather information on the current understanding of the impact of indoor and outdoor green plants on the indoor environment, we conducted a thorough search of databases such as Science Direct, Google Scholar, and Web of Science.

4. Result

The results of this research indicate that green facades have numerous potential benefits in improving indoor air quality. The integration of botanical biofilters into indoor spaces can effectively prevent pollutants from entering and purifying the air through various mechanisms.

One of the main advantages of green facades is their ability to act as a physical barrier, trapping and filtering out particulate matter and absorbing harmful gases. This significantly improves overall air quality indoors and reduces the risk of respiratory issues and allergies.

Additionally, green facades can purify the air through biological processes. Plants could absorb and metabolize airborne pollutants, converting them into harmless byproducts through phytoremediation. This further enhances indoor air quality [49].

Green facades offer several advantages in terms of air filtration:

Coverage and Plant Density: A green wall can contain over a thousand plants, all of which filter air and create energy-rich oxygen. In contrast, filling a room with enough traditional houseplants to make a meaningful difference in air quality would be impractical [50].

Active Vegetation Systems: Green facades, especially when combined with mechanical fans, may yield higher air-cleaning rates compared to passive vegetation systems. By actively circulating the air and increasing airflow, these systems enhance pollutant removal efficiency [49].

Maintenance and Irrigation: Both green facades and traditional houseplants require maintenance, but green facades may have their own controlled irrigation systems, making them more self-sufficient in terms of watering.

Selection of Plant Species: Different plant species have varying capacities for pollutant removal. Green facades can be designed with suitable plant species for the specific indoor environment, maximizing their air purification potential [50].

Selection of Plant Species: Different plant species have varying capacities for pollutant removal. Green facades can be designed with suitable plant species for the specific indoor environment, maximizing their air purification potential [49].

Humidity Control: Appropriate humidity levels must be maintained to prevent indoor air quality issues. Green facades can help regulate humidity levels, contributing to a healthier indoor environment [49].

In addition to their air purification benefits, green facades also have positive psychological impacts on occupants. Exposure to nature and greenery has a calming effect, leading to improved mental well-being, increased productivity, and overall satisfaction with the indoor environment [1, 51, 52].

5. Conclusion

In conclusion, the use of green facades to improve indoor air quality has been shown to have numerous potential benefits. Research suggests that green facades can effectively prevent pollutants from entering indoor spaces and purify the air through various mechanisms. The integration of botanical biofilters into indoor spaces not only improves air quality but also has positive psychological impacts on occupants, potentially enhancing their well-being and productivity.

One of the main advantages of green facades is their ability to act as a physical barrier, preventing outdoor pollutants from entering indoor spaces. The plants and vegetation in the facade can trap and filter out particulate matter, such as dust and pollen, as well as absorb

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harmful gases, such as carbon dioxide and volatile organic compounds. This can greatly improve the overall air quality indoors and reduce the risk of respiratory issues and allergies. In addition to acting as a physical barrier, green facades also can purify the air through biological processes. Plants are known for their ability to absorb and metabolize airborne pollutants, converting them into harmless byproducts through a process known as phytoremediation. This can effectively remove harmful substances from the air, further improving indoor air quality.

The use of active vegetation systems, such as green facades combined with mechanical fans, may yield higher air-cleaning rates compared to passive vegetation systems. By actively circulating the air and increasing airflow, these systems can enhance the efficiency of pollutant removal. However, further investigations are needed to fully understand the capacity of plants in real-life settings and to optimize the design and operation of these active systems.

It is important to note that the effectiveness of green facades in improving indoor air quality is highly dependent on the careful selection of plant species, maintenance, and humidity control. Different plant species have varying capacities for pollutant removal, so it is crucial to choose plants that are well-suited for the specific indoor environment. Regular maintenance, including pruning and watering, is necessary to ensure the health and vitality of the plants. Additionally, maintaining appropriate humidity levels is important to prevent the growth of mold and other indoor air quality issues.

Furthermore, the integration of green facades into indoor spaces can have positive psychological impacts on occupants. Numerous studies have shown that exposure to nature and greenery has a calming and stress-reducing effect on individuals. This can lead to improved mental well-being, increased productivity, and overall satisfaction with the indoor environment.

While the research on green facades to improve indoor air quality is promising, there is still much to learn. Future studies should focus on evaluating pollutant-removal mechanisms, selecting appropriate plant species, and designing active systems with mechanical ventilation. Additionally, long-term studies in real-life settings are needed to fully understand the capacity and limitations of green facades in improving indoor air quality.

Overall, this research highlights the potential of green facades as a sustainable solution for improving indoor air quality. By harnessing the natural abilities of plants and vegetation, we can create healthier and more pleasant indoor environments for occupants. The integration of green facades not only improves air quality but also has positive psychological impacts, making it a valuable addition to sustainable building design.

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